

HIRDLS Data at the BADC

<http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/hirdls/>

**National Centre for
Atmospheric Science**
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

**BRITISH
ATMOSPHERIC
DATA
CENTRE**

CCLRC
Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

What we have

- L0
 - From 21st July 2004
- L2 first products v2.00 (released 30-06-2006)
 - 2006 day numbers 124-142, 144-151 (*ie 4th-31st May 2006 -not 23rd*)
 - HDF-EOS 5 format
 - 1 data file, plus 1 metadata file per day
 - 4 parameters:*
 - *temperature,*
 - *ozone,*
 - *HNO₃,*
 - *cloud top pressure.*

What we hope to get next...

- End of September 2006 - Next release of Level 2 data from end Jan 06 to present day
- End of December 2006 - TBD

Where to find it

BADC HIRDLS web page

<http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/hirdls/>

- Links to archive -data & documentation
- Instructions on how to access archive
- Links to other HIRDLS websites

3 HIRDLS welcome page - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by SSTD Office Systems

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The High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder (HIRDLS)

First release of **Level 2 data** is now available at the BADC

Introduction

HIRDLS is an infrared limb-scanning radiometer designed to sound the upper troposphere, stratosphere, and mesosphere to determine temperature; the concentrations of O₃, H₂O, CH₄, N₂O, NO₂, HNO₃, N₂O₅, ClONO₂, CFC₁₂, CFC₁₃, and aerosols; and the locations of polar stratospheric clouds and cloud tops. The goals are to provide sounding observations with horizontal and vertical resolution superior to that previously obtained; to observe the lower stratosphere with improved sensitivity and accuracy; and to improve understanding of chemical processes through data analysis, diagnostics, and use of two- and three-dimensional models.

HIRDLS is part of the **Aura mission**, part of NASA's **Earth Observing System (EOS)**. Aura was successfully launched on 15th July 2004 at 9 a.m. BST from Vandenberg Air Force Base, California. HIRDLS is a joint US-UK endeavour effort, with sponsorship from the **National Space Centre and the Natural Environment Research Council in the UK**, and by **NASA** in the US.

The data received by the ground station, is processed at the University of Boulder Science Processing Suite (SIPS) before being archived at the Distributed Active Archive Center (DAAC). As HIRDLS is a joint US-UK programme, the BADC will mirror the data stored in the DAAC for ease of access. This **BADC data** will be subject to the same access constraints as the data in the DAAC. HIRDLS data is currently being collected and several teams are undertaking calibration and validation studies. Further information on this work can be seen on the [validation status page](#).

The HIRDLS **Level 2 data** mirrored from the DAAC will eventually be publicly available at the BADC, but initially it will be restricted to the HIRDLS science and validation teams and to those working on HIRDLS related projects. Members of HIRDLS related science projects should [apply for access to the hirdls archive here](#). Initially a few days worth of data from May 2006 are available. Further data and re-processed versions will follow.

The data for the high level products will be in **HDF5** format with the **EOS** extension. The lower level products will be in an instrument specific binary format. Level 0 data is currently available to the validation team.

Restricted Data Access

Access to the data will initially be restricted to the HIRDLS science team, and to holders of HIRDLS related grants.

To apply for access to the hirdls archive:

1. You will need your BADC username and password. New users [register here](#). For a reminder of your login details contact the [BADC Helpdesk](#).
2. [Apply for access to the hirdls archive](#). You will need to agree to the [HIRDLS conditions of use](#) and your application be approved by the HIRDLS UK co-PI. This may take a few days to complete.

After a validation period the released data will be made available to the public. The preliminary data are only intended for use by the HIRDLS validation team.

Documentation

Documentation to describe the [data format](#) and [software](#) to assist in the viewing of the data files are available. Users of the Level 2 data are directed to read and note the [documentation about data quality](#). (NB to read this you must have access to the data).

The BADC archive also stores [documentation](#) about the HIRDLS instrument and mission.

Links to Further Information

The main HIRDLS sites are

- The HIRDLS programme site at UCAR - <http://www.eos.ucar.edu/hirdls/>
- The HIRDLS instrument site at Oxford University - <http://www.atm.ox.ac.uk/hirdls/home.htm>
- The HIRDLS UK project office - <http://www.ssd.rl.ac.uk/hirdls/default.htm>

See also

- Information on **HDF5** format.
- Information on the **HDF-EOS** extension.

Who to Contact

If you have queries about these pages or about obtaining the HIRDLS data from the BADC then you should contact [BADC Support](#).

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<http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/>

HIRDLS data at BADC

Get Data - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by SSTD Office Systems

Address: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/data_browser/data_browser/badc/hirdls/

Links: BADC, BADC - Trac, Data Archive

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Current directory: / badc / hirdls

Dataset: High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder (HIRDLS) [Catalogue record](#) [Dataset web page](#)

High Resolution Dynamic Limb Sounder - Archive Dataset

- 00README 263 bytes
- data HIRDLS Data archive
- docs HIRDLS Support Documentation
- sampledata HIRDLS Sample data files and software
- software Software to read HIRDLS data files
- supportdata Useful supporting data

Get Data - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by SSTD Office Systems

Address: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/data_browser/data_browser/badc/hirdls/data

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Dataset: High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder (HIRDLS) [Catalogue record](#) [Dataset web page](#)

HIRDLS Data archive

- 00README 688 bytes
- auxiliary_files
- level0
- level1
- level2 HIRDLS Level 2 data - first release

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Get Data - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by SSTD Office Systems

Address: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/data_browser/data_browser/badc/hirdls/docs

Links: BADC, BADC - Trac, Data Archive

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Dataset: High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder (HIRDLS) [Catalogue record](#) [Dataset web page](#)

HIRDLS Support Documentation

- 00README 402 bytes
- 00link_to_ucar_hirdls_website.html 96 bytes
- atbd HIRDLS Algorithm Theoretical Basis Documents
- data_format
- l2_data_release_documentation
- papers
- posters_and_presentations
- validation_reports

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<http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/d>

Access restrictions

- All data currently restricted to validation teams.
- To access HIRDLS data at BADC
 1. Need BADC username and password
 2. Apply for access to HIRDLS data via link from web page
 - Agree to conditions of use online
 - Access granted at discretion of John Barnett

Other sources

- GES-DAAC (Goddard Earth Sciences - Distributed Active Archive Center)
 - <http://daac.gsfc.nasa.gov/>
- AVDC (Aura Validation Data Centre)
 - <http://avdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/>
 - Also contains correlative data

Tools to read the data

- IDL
 - `get_aura.pro` available at BADC
- Fortran and C/C++
 - Need both HDF5 and HDF-EOS5 Libraries -links available in software directory

User Support

See BADC HIRDLS web page

<http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/hirdls/>

Any queries

contact **Wendy Garland**

email **w.e.garland@rl.ac.uk**

or via BADC helpdesk **badc@rl.ac.uk**